

A Non-electrolyte Analogue of Teorell Membrane Oscillator

R. C. SRIVASTAVA*, O. P. SINGH and A. K. DAS

Department of Chemistry, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 4 August 1993

A non-electrolyte analogue of Teorell membrane oscillator is described. In these experiments aqueous solution of urea has been experimented with.

Teorell's celebrated experiments^{1,2} on oscillatory transport through artificial membranes continue to evoke interest even today^{3,4}, in view of their possible relevance to electrophysiology of neurons particularly generation of action potentials etc. Mueller and Rudin^{5,6} showed that the lipid bilayers prepared by them were not electrically excitable unless channel forming peptides or excitability inducing material (EIM) were incorporated in them. However, passive spread of electrical potentials is common and in many neurons that have very short axons or no axons at all, these cells often have few or no voltage gated Na⁺ channels and rely for their signalling entirely on passive spread, manifest as smoothly graded local potentials⁷. It is because of this fact that one is tempted to look at Teorell's work as a possible model of the neuron. Several workers have in fact demonstrated³ electrical excitability in the absence of any channel former or EIM. Since transport of Na⁺ and K⁺ ions is crucial to the generation of action potentials, all such efforts have been made using electrolyte solutions particularly sodium and potassium chlorides^{3,8-10}. The impression one gets from these studies is that the phenomenon of electrically induced oscillatory transport in artificial membranes is limited to electrolytic systems only.

In the present communication we report experiments which demonstrate that it is not so. Even suitable non-electrolytes in a Teorell type experimental set-up exhibit the phenomenon of oscillatory transport. In this communication we report our experiments with aqueous urea.

It must be mentioned that in addition to being relevant to electrophysiology of neurons, studies on Teorell type membrane oscillations are important in their own right because they lead to the

understanding of general phenomena of physiochemical instabilities in the far from equilibrium region. This fact is revealed by several thorough studies documented in the literature^{3,11} particularly those by Meares and Page^{12,13} and by Kobatake and Fujita¹⁴.

Results and Discussion

As pointed out by Meares and Page¹³, the basic ingredients which make the oscillations possible are at least two independent transport processes driven by different forces and that the flows induced by these forces oppose each other. In the present experiments and also in the Teorell's experiments¹ the pressure driven volume flow and the electro-osmotic volume flow opposed each other. In addition, the system should have at least two stable steady states and also an inbetween region of fragile stability. The balance point, e.g. in the present case, the state corresponding to no net volume flux ($J_v = 0$), should fall in the region of fragile stability. The oscillatory behaviour consists of repeated transitions between the two stable stationary states. Therefore, the first step towards locating the conditions under which oscillations would be observed is to discover the region of fragile stability and see whether or not the state of no net flux falls in that region.

The data obtained on volume flux J_v induced by pressure difference ΔP in the presence of constant currents (I) are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2. These plots clearly demonstrate the existence of two stable steady states along with the region of fragile stability. In the present system the two possible steady states are : (i) when the pores of the membrane are filled with urea solution and (ii) when they are filled with water. These two steady states respectively correspond to the portions AB

and CD in Fig. 1 and portions EF and GH in Fig. 2. The regions shown by the dotted lines in the Figs. 1 and 2 are the regions of fragile stability which are not experimentally accessible. A perusal of Figs. 1 and 2 also reveals that the state of no net flux $J_v = 0$ falls in the stable steady state region when $I = 0.1$ mA (Fig. 1) but when $I = 0.2$ mA it falls in the unstable region (Fig. 2). Therefore, one should not expect any oscillatory behaviour when $I = 0.1$ mA. In this way one gets an estimate of the threshold value of current below which oscillations should not be expected.

Fig. 1. Plot of volume flux (J_v) against pressure difference (ΔP) in the presence of a constant current (0.1 mA) using 3 M aqueous urea.

We, therefore, passed a constant current of 0.2 mA through the membrane and monitored the

Fig. 2. Plot of volume flux (J_v) against pressure difference (ΔP) in the presence of a constant current (0.2 mA) using 3 M aqueous urea.

transmembrane potential with time and as expected, we did get oscillations. A typical trace is shown in Fig. 3. In these experiments a pressure difference ($\Delta P = 22.15$ cm of urea solution column) which

corresponds to a value of J_v in the unstable region shown by dotted lines in Fig. 2, was initially imposed across the membrane.

The transmembrane potentials (Fig. 3) should on a priori grounds, be the algebraic sum of the ohmic potential and the streaming potential. The pores of the membrane get alternately filled with urea solution and with water; the solutions of differing conductivities. Since a constant current is passed through the membrane, the ohmic potential difference should vary with time depending upon whether the pores are filled with urea solution or with water. The streaming potentials would arise when the pressure driven liquid through the pores would carry along with it the mobile phase of the double layer inside the pores and create charge separation.

Fig. 3. A typical trace of transmembrane potential with time ($I = 0.2$ mA).

Conclusion : Thus the oscillatory behaviour observed in Teorell's experiments is not a preserve of electrolytic solutions, even non-electrolytic solutions can show oscillatory behaviour. The only requirement appears to be that the solutions should be able to generate an electrical double layer inside the pores otherwise the electro-osmotic volume flux opposing the pressure driven volume flux would be absent.

Experimental

The all-glass transport cell designed for the present studies is depicted in Fig. 4 which has been well labelled to make it self explanatory. The two compartments, one containing 3 M urea solution and then other containing water, were separated by a Sartorius microfiltration membrane (Cat. no. 11107, pore size $0.2 \mu\text{m}$). Since the electro-osmotic flow, as determined by a separate experiment, was

from positive to negative electrode, the electrode in the chamber containing urea solution and that in the chamber containing water were connected respectively to the negative and the positive terminals of an electronically operated stabilised power supply (Systronics 610) and pressure was applied to the compartment containing urea

pressure difference across the membrane. A known constant current I was driven through the membrane using electrodes E_1 and E_2 and the transmembrane potentials were monitored with time through the sensing calomel electrodes connected to a $x-t$ recorder (Digital Electronics, model Omniscrite B-5000).

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of the Teorell type membrane oscillator using urea solution : (E_1 , E_2) bright platinum electrodes, (L_1' , L_2') capillary, (M) Sartorius cellulose acetate microfiltration membrane and (S, T) stop-cocks.

solution. Two types of studies were conducted : one, demonstrating the existence of two stable steady states in the system along with an inbetween region of fragile stability and the other in which oscillations in transmembrane potentials, consequent to driving a constant current through the membrane, were demonstrated.

To demonstrate the existence of two stable steady states and the region of fragile stability in the system a constant current (I) was passed through the membrane, and the data on net volume flux (J_v) in the presence of various pressure differences (ΔP) across the membrane obtained. The volume flux J_v was measured by noting the rate of advancement of the liquid meniscus in the capillary L_1' L_2' using a cathetometer reading upto 10^{-5} m and a stop-watch reading upto 0.1 s.

To demonstrate the oscillations in transmembrane potential the pressure head and the horizontal capillary L_1' L_2' were replaced by vertical tubes and the level of the liquids in them was suitably adjusted to create the desired initial

In these experiments the polarities of the electrodes E_1 and E_2 were so adjusted that the electro-osmotic flow opposed the flow due to ΔP . All experiments were conducted at constant temperature using a thermostat set at $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Urea (AnalaR) and deionised water distilled twice in an all-pyrex glass still were used in these experiments.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for funding this research. One of the authors (A.K.D.) thanks U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of a Fellowship.

References

1. T. TEORELL, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1959, **42**, 831.
2. T. TEORELL, *J. Gen. Physiol.*, 1959, **42**, 847.
3. R. LARTER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 355.
4. J. T. KIM and R. LARTER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1991, **95**, 7948.
5. P. MUELLER and D. O. RUDIN, *Nature*, 1967, **213**, 603.
6. P. MUELLER and D. O. RUDIN, *Nature*, 1968, **217**, 713.

1. B. ALBERTS, D. BRAY, J. LEWIS, M. RAFF, K. ROBERTS and J. D. WATSON, "Molecular Biology of the Cell", 2nd. ed., Garland, New York, 1989, p. 1066.
8. H. C. PANT and B. ROSENBERG, *Biochim. Biophys. Acta*, 1971, **225**, 379.
9. V. E. SHASHOUA, *Nature*, 1967, **215**, 846.
10. V. F. ANTONOV, V. V. PETROV, A. A. MOLNAR, D. A. PREDVODITELEV and A. S. IVANOV, *Nature*, 1980, **283**, 585.
11. S. R. CAPLAN and D. C. MIKULECKY, in "Ion Exchange", ed. J. A. MARINSKY, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1966, Vol. I, pp. 1-64.
12. P. MEARES and K. R. PAGE, *Phil. Trans R Soc., London, Ser. A*, 1972, **272**, 1.
13. P. MEARES and K. R. PAGE, *Proc. R. Soc., Ser. A*, 1974, **339**, 513.
14. Y. KOBATAKE and H. FUJITA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1964, **40**, 2212, 2219.